

Development and Characterization of Shea Butter Seed Husk Carbon Black for Cyanide bearing Wastewater Treatment

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ABSTRACT

Batch adsorption of cyanide ions from aqueous solution using activated carbon developed from Shea Butter Seed Husk (SBSH) was investigated. The Shea butter seed husk was removed from the seed using mortar and pestle, it was then washed, dried and carbonized/Calcined at 450oC - 500oC and activated at 700oC using hydrochloric acid. The effect of adsorbent dose, initial cyanide concentration, contact time and pH were investigated and found to significantly affect the adsorption capacity with optimum adsorbent dose, contact time and initial cyanide concentration of 3.0g/100ml, 120mins and 100mg/l. The removal efficiency of cyanide ions by SBSH carbon black was 94.56% at lower concentration of 100mg/l and 58.7% was achieved at higher concentration of 600mg/l cyanide concentration.

Keywords: Cyanide ion, Adsorbent Dosage, Calcination, Shea Butter Seed Husk, Activated Carbon.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental safety and ill-free existence has been one of human target since time immemorial. The creation of safe drinking water and prevention of environmental hazards had kept scientists researching on daily basis to achieve these goals. The decontamination of sites from industrial wastes and other aspects of endeavours led to vast Research Methodologies and Models (RMM). Several methods such as ion exchange, solvent extraction, reverse osmosis, precipitation, and adsorption had been proposed and developed for the treatment of wastewater contaminated with heavy metals and other toxic effluents [1]. Adsorption using activated carbon from the agricultural wastes are the most widely used industrial adsorbent for removing pollutants from gaseous, aqueous and non aqueous streams, due to their uniquely powerful adsorption properties and the ability to readily modify their surface chemistry [2].

Biological process is generally the preferred technique for treating wastewater owing to its cost-effectiveness and environmental easiness. There is little work on the use of bioprocesses for treatment of cyanide-laden wastewater [3, 4]. Another conventional method for cyanide removal is Chemical process [5]. It is uninvited technique because it requires the various chemical and reagents and secondary pollutants are created, furthermore, it also needs some additional treatment prior to its disposal. Chemical processes of cyanide removal are not appropriate for environmental and economic perspectives [6]. Adsorption processes through the use of agricultural waste material have been recently employed for toxic waste removal due to its availability, low energy consumption, cost effectiveness and eco-friendly nature [7].

Adsorption is a simple and attractive method for the removal of toxic compounds from effluents due to its high efficiency, easy handling and economic feasibility. Adsorption systems are not affected by the toxicity of the target compound(s) and do not require hazardous chemicals. Moreover, adsorption

facilitates concentrating and then recovering the adsorbed compounds if desired [8]. Bio-sorption of cyanide from aqueous solutions is quite a new process that has confirmed very promising in the removal of contaminants from aqueous effluents. Various agro based adsorbents have been reported for cyanide removal from water and wastewater due to their abundant availability and low cost [8]. However, industrial wastewater mainly from electroplating and mining industries normally contains higher cyanide concentration such as 5-250 mg/L [9] and there is very little literature on the removal of cyanide from water containing cyanide at higher concentration. For making adsorption process more feasible and cost effective, there is urgent need of low cost adsorbents with higher adsorption capacities.

Activated carbon has a great potential for cyanide waste treatment both in gold extraction plants and effluent from metal finishing plants and hence, it forms a subject studied in the present work.

Characterization of activated carbon shows that surface area has an effect, although the reactivity of the surface is as a result of oxygenated functional groups. The highly active surface properties of the activated carbon are attributed to the chemical functional groups and the internal surface areas, which typically range from 500 to 3000mg/g [7].

Water is polluted in many ways like effluent of leather and chemical industries, electroplating industries and dye industries [10]. Several industrial and agricultural processes and mining activities have increased the concentration of toxic contamination in water and waste water around the world.

Water is considered polluted if some substances or condition is present to such a degree that the water cannot be used for a specific purpose. Olaniran [11] defined water pollution to be the presence of excessive amounts of a hazard (pollutants) in water in such a way that it is no longer suitable for drinking, bathing, cooking or other uses. Pollution is the introduction of a

contamination into the environment [12]. It is created by industrial and commercial waster, agricultural practices, everyday human activities and most notably, models of transportation. No matter where you go and what you do, there are remnants earths environmental and its inhabitants in many ways.

Water pollution has a duel effect on nature. It has negative effects on the living and also on the environment. The effects of pollution on human beings and aquatic communities are many and varied. Water pollution causes approximately 14,000 deaths per day, mostly due to contamination of drinking water by untreated sewage. Diversity of communities is to be expected when large amount of toxic materials especially heavy metals, cyanide and so on are released into the streams, lakes and coastal waters in the ocean. Much of aquatic pollution involves sewage in which organic waste predominate. This waste can increase secondary productivity while altering the character of the aquatic community. Most fishes especially the species desired as food by man are among the sensitive species that disappear with the least intense pollution.

Water polluted by cyanide lead to damage on human health. Drinking water is affected and health hazards result. Acid rain which lowers the pH value of soil and emission of carbon dioxide cause ocean acidification, the ongoing decrease in the pH of the Earth's Oceans as CO₂ becomes dissolved.

The pertinent parameters that influence adsorption such as Initial Cyanide (CN^-) Concentration (ICC), Agitation Time (t), pH and Adsorbent Dosage (AD) were investigated.

In this study, adsorption processes with the use of Carbon Black (CB) prepared from Shea Butter Seed Husk (SBSH) has been explored due to its eco-friendly nature and availability in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The material used for this research work, shea butter (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) seed were collected free of no cost from farmlands in Sabon Gida Tukura, Kurmi Local Government Area and Gidan Idi, Wukari Local Government, Taraba State, Nigeria. The *shea butter* seed were washed severally with surface water to remove attached films such as the fleshy layers, soil and dusts to expose the indehiscent seed cuticle (husk). The seed husks were removed by dehusking using mortar and pestle and washed with double distilled water and Oven dried. For the preparation of the adsorbent, the dried and grinded sample was calcined at 500°C for physical preparation. Chemical activation of the prepared carbon black sample was done by treating it with dilute hydrochloric acid until paste was formed which was then carbonized again at a temperature of 650-700°C in the furnace for 2 hours. The black product obtained was dried in an oven for 12 hours at 100°C and passed through 750µm sieve size for regulating the uniform particles, hence, the carbonized sample was washed severally with de-ionized water until an approximate pH of 7 was attained, it was filtered with Whatman №1 filter paper and again dried for 8 hours at 110°C in the oven and stored in air-tight plastic containers as adopted by [13] and shown pictorially in Figure 1.

About 100mg of KCN in 1000ml was prepared from the stock solution of 6.56g KCN in 1000ml solution with KOH pellet. Other concentrations were prepared by serial dilution of the Cyanide (stock). All other chemicals used for the preparation of adsorbent and for adsorption tests were of analytical grade and were used without further purification.

Characterization of the Adsorbent

The physical properties, Ultimate analysis and surface morphology of the prepared activated carbon from *shea butter* seed husk were studied and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Ultimate Analysis and Physical Properties of Shea Butter Seed Husk Carbon Black

Physical Properties						Elemental Analysis			
Ash (%)	V _M (%)	FC (%)	M (%)	BD (g/cm ³)	SG (g/cm ³)	H	C	N	S
1.37	69.3	0.69	4.0	0.95	1.86	5.2	61.3	0.56	0.009

V_M = Volatile Matter, M = Moisture Content, FC= Fixed Carbon, BD = Bulk Density, SG = Specific Gravity

Table 2: Time, Adsorbent Dosage, pH and Initial Cyanide Concentration Operating Parameters for Cyanide ions Removal

Batch Operation Objective	Operating Parameters
To study the effect of Initial Cyanide Concentration on Cyanide ion Removal	Adsorbent Dosage: 3.0g/100ml; Temp 30°C; Time 120min; pH 10; ICC: 100-600mg/L
To study the effect of Contact Time on Cyanide ion Removal	Adsorbent Dosage: 3.0g/100mg; Temp 30°C; ICC: 100mg/L; pH 10; Time: 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, 105, 120 minutes.
To study the effect of pH on Cyanide ion Removal	Adsorbent Dosage:3.0g/100ml; ICC:100mg/L; Temp:30°C; Time: 120min; pH 2-12
To study the effect of Adsorbent Dosage on Cyanide ion Removal	ICC: 100mg/L; Temp; 30°C; Time: 120min; pH 10; Adsorbent Dosage: 0.5-4.0g/100ml

Where ICC: Initial Cyanide Concentration

Experimental Set-Up

Three sets of batch mode operation were conducted on prepared adsorbent in order to measure the adsorption behaviour of cyanide contained before and after adsorption. Thus, in a

representative experiment, 0.5 - 4.0g of dried adsorbent was shaken with 100ml of the stock solution at varying concentration at 30°C for 90minutes. After equilibrium, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate was treated with prepared picric solution for colorimetric analysis for the remaining cyanide ions concentration. Ranges of operating parameters for the various batch operations are shown in Table 2.

Adsorption of cyanide ions were measured by shaking (using mechanical shaker) 0.5-4.0g of the adsorbent in 100ml solution of 100mg/L concentration of cyanide for 90minutes. The Initial Cyanide Concentration (ICC) was also varied in the range between 100-600mg/L for the same time (90mins) at an adsorbent dose of 3.0g. Percentage adsorption for each sample was calculated according to Equation 1, where C_i and C_e (mg/L) represents the initial and equilibrium concentration, respectively.

The amount of adsorbed cyanides (q_e , mg/g) were calculated by the mass balance calculation of cyanide ion before and after the adsorption as expressed by Equation 2. Where, V (l) is the volume of the test solution used and W (g) is the dry weight of the adsorbent.

$$\% A = \frac{C_i - C_e}{C_i} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$Q = \frac{C_i - C_e}{W} \times V \quad (2)$$

Instrumental Analysis

Replicate samples were prepared in triplicates by transferring known amount of adsorbent into the solution in 250ml Erlenmeyer flask for statistical treatment, in which certain simple percentage was used to determine the amount of cyanide removal. While determinate errors were minimized by running blank. Free cyanide and weak acid cyanide in the filtrate reacts with picric acid reagent to produce an orange colour that can be measured colorimetrically at the wavelength of 520nm (Microprocessor UV/VIS Single Beam Spectrophotometer; model T60).

The dissolved base/alkali metal picrate was converted by the cyanide to the coloured salt of iso-purpuric acid, Figure 6.

Figure 1: Shea Butter Seed Husk Before and After Calcinations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section gives vivid details of results obtained from the preparation, characterization and the Spectrometric study of batch

adsorption of an adsorbent prepared from Shea butter seed husks and tends to discuss the effects of: Adsorbent Dosage (AD), pH, Contact Time, and Initial Cyanide Concentration on the adsorption of cyanide ions from aqueous solution using the adsorbent prepared from Shea butter seed husk (SBSH).

Effect of Adsorbent Dosage on Cyanide ions Removal by SBSH Carbon Black

Figure 2: Effect of Adsorbent Dosage on Cyanide ions Removal by SBSH Carbon Black

The effect of adsorbent dose on cyanide ions removal was investigated under the conditions in Table 2. According to Figure 2, the removal of cyanide ions was found to vary within 60 - 80% at dose less than 3.0g. But at exactly 3.0g/100ml, there was a significant increase in cyanide removal up to 94.56% which remains almost constant at dose 3.5-4.0g/ml. Since the increase in adsorbent dosage increases the number of active sites, this enhances the percentage removal up to 3.0g/100ml where maximum adsorption occurs. Bhumica *et al.*, [14] reported 82% cyanide removal at dose 40g/L coal fly ash after 48hrs time, and Naveen *et al.*, [15] also reported 91.5% cyanide removal when almond shell dosage was 20g/L at 90minutes. The Shea butter seed husk bio-adsorbent used in this work is of course more effective, removing about 94.56% cyanide ions in wastewater at a dose of 3.0g/100ml of 100mg/L cyanide solution at 2hrs with R^2 value of 0.878 showing that an increase in adsorbent dosage within the stipulated condition will enhance cyanide ions removal.

Effect of Contact Time on Cyanide ions Removal by SBSH Carbon Black

Figure 3: Effect of Contact Time on Cyanide ions Removal by SBSH Carbon Black

Effect of contact Time was investigated based on the condition given in Table 2. Figure 3 shows that, at least 82% cyanide removal was achieved for 100mg/L of cyanide solution at 15 minutes. Hence, the equilibrium removal efficiencies of cyanide were 94.56% at 120minute with R^2 value of 0.837. This implies high favourability of Shea butter seed husk carbon black for the adsorption of cyanide ions from aqueous solution.

Effect of Initial Cyanide Concentration on Cyanide ions Removal by SBSH Carbon Black

Figure 4: Effect of Initial Cyanide Concentration on Cyanide ions Removal by SBSH Carbon Black

Table 2 shows the influence of varying Initial Cyanide Concentration (ICC) from 100mg/L to 600mg/L under the stated conditions. Figure 4 shows the adsorption result obtained by varying initial cyanide concentration at 3.0g/100ml adsorbent dosage. Based on the plotted data, 94.56% cyanide removal was achieved at lower concentration of 100mg/L whereas about 58.7% was achieved at higher cyanide concentration of about 600mg/L. The reduction of cyanide removal as an efficacy of its concentration can be explained by the restriction of available free sites on the adsorbent for the adsorption of cyanide with increased cyanide concentration in bulk solution for a fixed mass of the adsorbent, as well as by the increase in intra - particle diffusion [16]. This is evident in the R^2 value of 0.971 which shows clearly that as the concentration of the cyanide ions increases in the bulk solution, limited sites are available for the adsorption process. Hence, the more the ions, the less the removal efficiency.

Effect of pH on Cyanide ions Removal by SBSH Carbon Black

The effect of pH was investigated in accordance to the conditions stated in Table 2. Based on Figure 5, solution pH played an important role in the removal of cyanide ion from aqueous solution. At pH <10, the adsorption remains almost constantly maximum due to effect created by sulphuric acid used for pH regulation. Only at pH 10 - 12 that significant drop in percentage removal was noticed. It thus could be assumed that; either the hydrogen ion (H^+) from the sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) reacted with the cyanide ions of the solution forming a volatile hydrocyanic acid (hydrogen cyanide, HCN) loss from the solution or the sulphuric acid reactivated the adsorbent (by creation of free sites) for efficient cyanide adsorption.

Figure 5: Effect of pH on Cyanide ions Removal by SBSH Carbon Black

Figure 6: Colorimetric Analysis of the Cyanide Ions based on their Concentrations when reacted with Picric Acid.

CONCLUSION

The development and characterization of SBSH Carbon black was carried out effectively and efficiently. The adsorption process went on smoothly. Therefore, it would be concluded that, for an optimum performance of the adsorption process, the pH was ≈ 10 , adsorbent dosage was 3.0g/100ml, temperature was $30 \pm 2^\circ C$ and Cyanide concentration was 100mg/l. The removal efficiency of cyanide ions by SBSH carbon black was 94.56% at lower concentration of 100mg/l and 58.7% was achieved at higher concentration of 600mg/l cyanide concentration. The SBSH carbon black produced has proven to have high adsorption capacity and a low cost bio - adsorbent which is an eco - friendly product that can remove cyanide ions from wastewater at a minimal contact time using suitable operating conditions.

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